

Problem-Based Learning-Path Recommendations Through Integrating Knowledge Graphs and Large Language Models

Hasan Abu-Rasheed^{1,*}, Rika Ikeda^{2,*}, Andrey Ferriyan^{2,*}, Christian Weber¹, Madjid Fathi¹, Keiko Okawa² and Achmad Husni Thamrin²

¹University of Siegen, Siegen, Germany

²Keio University, Tokyo, Japan

Abstract

Learning path recommendations are essential to acquire skill sets needed to solve real-life challenges. However, the main source of information that recommendation systems (RS) use to generate personalized paths is user data rather than the challenge that the user faces. In this research, we propose a problem-based approach to generate learning-path recommendations using knowledge graphs (KG) to connect learning materials, and large language models (LLM) for natural-language understanding and topic extraction. We construct a KG of courses and digital badges through human- and machine-extracted relations. Our RS analyzes a challenge written by the learner, extracts learning goals needed to solve that challenge, and then implements a Markov decision process (MDP) to select the optimal learning path. The learning path is then explained utilizing the KG and the LLM. We evaluate our KG relations in comparison to expert-defined tags. We also evaluate the recommendations and their explanations with a use-case approach. Our preliminary results show the ability of the proposed system to connect courses from different domains, recommend corresponding paths to the challenge requirements, and assign relevant explanations accordingly.

Keywords

Learning path, recommender systems, explainable recommendations, large language models (LLM), GPT-4, knowledge graphs

1. Introduction

Solving real-life challenges requires multiple skills due to their complexity. Learning path RS have been developed in recent years to offer learners a sequence of learning materials that can achieve a learning goal [1]. However, majority of RS use data about the learners themselves, e.g., in a user profile, to generate a personalized recommendation [1, 2]. Analyzing real-life challenges that learners face and defining their learning goals are still difficult for automated recommendations. Therefore, it has been handled by human mentors. In scenarios where a challenge is temporal or dynamic, and when human support might not always be available, RS are required to 1) analyze the challenge, 2) break it down to its main learning requirements, and 3) generate a personalized learning path that enables the learner to solve the problem. These three tasks are, in fact, tasks of natural language understanding, topic extraction, and learning path generation. The recent development of large language models (LLMs) offers great potential to handle the first two tasks and support the RS in performing the third one more effectively [3].

2. Proposed Approach

To accomplish the task of generating a learning path recommendation for a specific learning challenge, we developed an LLM-supported RS, which is based on a KG, to select, order, and recommend a set of courses that are relevant to the user-described challenge. In the proposed system, see Figure 1, users

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*Corresponding authors.

✉ hasan.abu.rasheed@uni-siegen.de (H. Abu-Rasheed); rika.ikeda@keio.jp (R. Ikeda); andrey@sfc.wide.ad.jp (A. Ferriyan)

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Figure 1: Proposed approach for an explainable, graph-based learning-path recommendation.

describe the challenges and learning needs in a free textual format. A GPT-4 LLM [4] then extracts the main topics from that description and phrase them as partial learning goals. We utilize prompt engineering to design a prompt context enriched with rules and contextual information from the KG, to mitigate the risk of model hallucination, irrelevant output, and too general responses. The KG is a network of connected entities, which include in our case *study programs*, *courses*, and *digital badges* [5]. To create the KG, we define a unique node type for each entity and connect the node using a hybrid approach, in which human-defined relations are complemented with a semantic relation extraction (RE) algorithm to enhance the connectivity of courses and badges. This offers more flexibility to navigate the KG and tailor the learning path recommendation to the problem at hand and the personal user profile. To generate the path recommendation, our RS:

1. Considers the user profile as the starting point for any learning path.
2. Identifies the group of partial goals extracted from the challenge description.
3. Creates temporary relations between the partial goals.
4. Uses MDP to explore all paths and assign weights to each one, based on its compatibility with the challenge description and the user profile.

The path with the highest weight is then recommended to the user.

The goal of creating temporary relations in the KG between the partial learning goals is to allow KG navigation algorithm to construct a learning path from multiple domains, which may not be connected by the human or the RE algorithm. An example in our case is programming and water management, which are semantically very different domains. Yet, both domains are necessary to solve, e.g., a challenge of analyzing geographic data in a flood crisis. We utilize an LLM-supported explainability approach to generate textual explanations of the learning path. Visual explanations are also generated from the KG and offered to the learner alongside the recommendation, supporting them in making an informed decision on the recommendation.

3. Preliminary Results

We evaluate the proposed approach on two levels: 1) evaluating the RE algorithm for KG creation, 2) evaluating the recommended paths and their explanations. The RE results are evaluated against human-defined relationships. We use the tags that creators defined in the course and badge metadata to indicate relations between elements that use the same tag. Semantic relations extracted by our algorithm from the textual descriptions of courses and badges covered 86.6% of the relations created through human-defined tags. To evaluate the explainable recommendations, we follow a use-case approach,

in which complex challenges are defined and explainable learning paths are generated for them. An example challenge format is: “A high level of pollution was discovered in a lake. I am organizing a team of volunteers to analyze the water supply data. For this task, I need to build a web page to support volunteers’ communication and write a Python program to automate the data analysis”. Recommended paths and explanations are then analyzed to evaluate three main measures:

1. correctness of topic extraction from the challenge
2. acceptance of the recommended topics to solve the challenge
3. acceptance of the path explanation

As a proof-of-concept, we used a set of 10 challenges, which were evaluated separately by 3 team members (one developer and two content experts) using a 1-5 Likert scale for each measure. Our preliminary result of the first prototype shows that the LLM-based challenge analysis scored 4.9/5 in identifying the main topics of the challenge. Recommending topics that are needed to solve the challenge scored an average of 4/5, while the path explanations scored 3.9/5. Our preliminary results also showed that the contextual information from the KG prevented the model from generating irrelevant texts. Textual explanations from the LLM were found to justify the connection to the challenge description. However, the LLM’s output failed in explaining domain-specific terms or abbreviations when a clear definition was not explicitly provided for them in the data base. This limitation was also a part of the lower score for explanations, due to metadata sparsity. Encouraged by the proof-of-concept evaluation phase, we designed an extended evaluation strategy in the form of a user study, where we will survey a larger sample size of users who will interact with the system and evaluate the resulting recommendations and their corresponding explanations.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we proposed an approach for generating explainable learning path recommendations, building on a KG, and utilizing LLMs for topic extraction from natural language. Our core contribution is generating learning path recommendations regarding a user-defined challenge alongside the user profile. This allows the path to be tailored specifically to a dynamic, urgent, or temporal problem the user faces. Our preliminary evaluation shows that the concept can achieve its promised tasks. A larger-scale user study, however, is required and will follow up this research for a deeper quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the proposed system.

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